

ISic1092

I.Sicily inscription 1092

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Partanna

Provenance

Found 1.5km outside Partanna, above Belice, in April 1880 (so IGPalermo)

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico Regionale Antonino Salinas,
inventory 8770

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 19.5 cm

Width 36.5 cm

Depth 2.5 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Θεοῖς · Καταχ(θονίοις) ·
2. Μαρκία Καίσαρος δ(ούλη)
3. ἔζησεν · ἔτη · λε ·
4. · Μύστις θυγατρὶ
5. · ἰδίᾳ · μνήμης χάριν ·

Apparatus

Text of IGPalermo compared against photograph

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284821

EDCS 39102250

PHI 140575

PHI 175629

Bibliography

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undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.
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Manganaro, G. 1988. La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. *ANRW*. 2.11.1: 3-89. At 49 and tav. 18.28

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